

Anti-inflammatory properties of haemolymph from the African giant land snails (*Acharchatina marginata* and *Achatina achatina*)

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Abstract: This study aims to ascertain the anti-inflammatory properties of haemolymph from the African giant land snails (*Acharchatina marginata* and *Achatina achatina*) in Ohaji/ Egbema Local Government Area, Imo State Nigeria. Giant African land snails were picked from the wild in Umuagwo, Umuokanne and Mgbirichi/ Abakuru communities of Ohaji/ Egbema Local Government Area of Imo State Nigeria. Identification of snails were based on their shell, feet, sizes and markings. The haemolymphs were collected aseptically from mature African giant land snails using standard methods. Biochemical analysis carried out in this study to ascertain the anti-inflammatory activity of the haemolymph of *Acharchatina marginata* and *Achatina achatina* include nitric oxide inhibition assay and inhibition of protein denaturation assay. The results revealed that inhibition of nitric oxide radicals by the haemolymph of *A. achatina* and *A. marginata* was higher than that of the quercetin standard. Similarly, the inhibition of protein oxidation by *A. achatina* and *A. marginata* haemolymph was demonstrated, although weaker than the Diclophenac standard as shown in the results of the present study. Further research could focus on optimization of these properties for biopharmaceutical applications.

Keywords: *Anti-Inflammatory Properties, African giant land snails, Haemolymph.*

Introduction

Snails have a high nutritive value and consequently the consumption of its meat has risen drastically over the years (1). Another good reason for the rising rate of snail meat consumption is because nowadays, many people are avoiding red meat for health reasons (2). Snail meat protein contain most of all the essential – amino acids (3, 4). Also, snail meat contains

minerals such as calcium, zinc, magnesium and iron (5). The snail meat has a protein content which ranges from 40% to 82.87% (6, 7). As a result of their unique biological features and their ability to adapt to changing environments, snails are being harnessed in many fields, for example in agriculture, medicine, food industry, cosmetics, biotechnology and environmental monitoring (8).

Haemolymph of the African giant snail is administered as oral rehydration therapy, and when combined with herbs is used in the treatment of diarrhoea and vomiting (9). Biochemical studies on the composition of snail haemolymph has been earlier suggested (10). The haemolymph of snail contains low concentrations of glyucose and sodium ions, moderate concentrations of bicarbonate, chloride ions and protein, and high levels of potassium and magnesium ions when compared with the normal human plasma (9). Snail haemolymph contains immunoglobulins which act as antibodies and thereby plays a vital role in the immune system (11).

Materials and Method

Snail Sample Collection

Snails were picked from the wild in Umuagwo, Umuokanne and Mgbirichi/ Abakuru communities of Ohaji/ Egbema Local Government Area of Imo State Nigeria.

Snail Identification

Identification of snails were based on their shape, size, markings, colour, spire angle, sculpture and aperture form (12).

Collection of Haemolymph

The haemolymphs were extracted from mature giant African land snails using standard methods.

Anti-inflammatory activity

Nitric oxide inhibition assay

Principle

The method is based on the bases that sodium nitroprusside in aqueous solution at physiological pH immediately yields nitric oxide which reacts with oxygen to give nitrite ions that can be measured using Griess reagent.

Procedure

The inhibitory effect of *A. marginata* and *A. achatina* haemolymph on nitric oxide was measured according to the method described by (13). The assay was done in 4 ml volume made up of different concentrations of *A. marginata* and *A. achatina* haemolymph (0 - 1000 µg/ml) and quercetin standard solution (0-1000 µg/ml) in phosphate buffer (pH. 7.2). 1ml of 5 mM sodium nitroprusside solution in phosphate buffer (pH. 7.2) was added to the tubes and then allowed to incubate at 29°C for 2 hours. Nitrite formed was measured by reacting 2 ml of the incubation solution with 1ml Griess reagent (equal volume of 1% sulphanilic acid and 0.1% N-(1-naphthyl) ethylene diamine dihydrochloride (NED). Measurement of the absorbance was done in a spectrophotometer at 550 nm. Inhibition of nitrite formation by haemolymph or

quercetin was calculated relative to the control which was void of haemolymph or quercetin.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Absorbance control} - \text{Absorbance test}}{\text{Absorbance control}} \times 100$$

Inhibition of protein denaturation Assay

The anti-inflammatory activity of *A. marginata* and *A. achatina* haemolymph was evaluated as described by (14). To determine the anti-inflammatory activity, 2 ml of varying concentration of the haemolymph ranging from (0-1000 µg/ml) was added to 2.8 mL of phosphate-buffered saline (pH 7.4), and 0.2 mL of a 1% aqueous solution of bovine serum albumin;

the cocktail was shaken to obtain a mixture with a total volume of 5 ml. The set-up was thereby incubated for 20 minutes at room temperature, then it was heated at 55°C for 30 minutes in a water bath. The samples were allowed to cool and the absorbance was measured using a spectrophotometer at 660 nm. The standard drug for comparison was diclofenac sodium. The percentage of protein denaturation was determined relative to control using the equation as follows:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Absorbance control} - \text{Absorbance test}}{\text{Absorbance control}} \times 100$$

Data analysis

The dose-response data from the assessment of inhibition of nitric oxide radicals and protein denaturation of the haemolymph were fitted into non-linear models using sigmaplot statistical software (version 10) to obtain the respective threshold inhibitory

concentration (IC₅₀). This is explained as the concentrations that achieved 50% inhibition. The percentage inhibition (y) data mainly fitted into logistic dose response model (LDR (a,b,c,) (equation 1), models with highest R² value and low fit standard error were chosen as best fit.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{100}{1 + \left(\frac{x}{IC_{50}}\right)^b} \quad (1)$$

As x implies the concentration of the haemolymph, IC_{50} implies the concentration that caused 50% inhibition; b implies the parameter determining the relative slope at IC_{50} .

Results

Experimental and model predicted response plot of inhibition of nitric oxide radical by haemolymph of A. marginata, A. achatina and Quercetin standard

Results presented in Figure 1 show the inhibitory effect *A. marginata* and *A. achatina* haemolymph and Quercetin standard on nitric oxide radical. *A. marginata* and *A. achatina* haemolymph inhibited sodium nitroprusside generated nitric oxide in a dose dependent manner. The inhibition of nitric oxide was predictable by a logistic dose response model equation with R^2 value of 0.995,

0.996 and 0.993 for *A. marginata* and *A. achatina* haemolymph and Quercetin respectively. The threshold inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) of haemolymph obtained from the two snail species were 321.86 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 119.46 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for *A. marginata* and *A. achatina* respectively, and 86.57 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for quercetin standard. These threshold inhibitory concentrations showed that *A. achatina* haemolymph was a more potent inhibitor of nitric oxide radical than *A. marginata* haemolymph. The values were closely comparable to those of quercetin standard.

Figure 1 Experimental and model predicted response plot of inhibition of nitric oxide radical by haemolymph of *A. marginata*, *A. achatina* and Quercetin standard

The results of experimental data and model predicted plot of inhibitory effect of *A. marginata* and *A. achatina* haemolymph and Diclofenac Sodium on protein oxidation are presented in Figure 2. The two snail species haemolymph showed significant inhibition of protein oxidation. However, comparatively *A. achatina* haemolymph showed higher inhibitory effect on heat induced protein oxidation than *A. marginata* haemolymph, but was lower than the

standard. The inhibition of induced protein oxidation followed a logistic dose response model equation with R² value of 0.978, 0.989 and 0.999 for *A. marginata*, *A. achatina* haemolymph and diclofenac sodium respectively. The threshold concentration for 50% inhibition of protein oxidation was 115.64 µg/ml, 69.23 µg/ml and 4.22 µg/ml for *A. marginata* and *A. achatina* haemolymph and diclofenac sodium respectively.

Figure 2 Experimental and model predicted response plot of protein oxidation inhibition by *A. marginata* serum, *A. achatina* haemolymph and Diclofenac Sodium

Table 1 The threshold inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀), and prediction model of Inhibition of nitric oxide radical and protein oxidation by *A. marginata*, *A. achatina* haemolymph and standards.

Sample/Standard	Inhibition of nitric oxide radical			Inhibition of protein oxidation		
	IC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	Mathematical model	R ²	IC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	Mathematical model	R ²
<i>A. marginata</i> haemolymph	321.87 ± 27.11	Logistic 3 parameter	0.995	115.64 ± 4.56	Logistic 3 parameter	0.978
<i>A. achatina</i> haemolymph	119.46 ± 7.32	Logistic 3 parameter	0.996	69.23 ± 3.01	Logistic 3 parameter	0.989
Quercetin dehydrate	86.57 ± 3.11	Logistic 3 parameter	0.993	-	-	-
Diclofenac sodium	-	-	-	4.22 ± 0.23	Logistic 3 parameter	0.999

Values are mean ± standard deviation of three determinations

Discussion

The inhibition of Nitric oxide radicals by the haemolymph of *A. achatina* and *A. marginata* was higher than that of the quercetin standard. Similarly, the inhibition of protein oxidation by *A. achatina* and *A. marginata* haemolymph was demonstrated, although weaker than the Diclophenac standard as shown in the results of the present study. Snails exhibit antioxidant and other anti-inflammatory properties, which contains various compounds that can scavenge free radicals and protect against oxidative stress (15). Previous studies have attributed these properties to components like allantoin, collagen, elastin, and antimicrobial peptides found in snail extracts (9, 11, 16). Snail extracts also contain other antioxidants, such as polyphenols, and enzymes like superoxide dismutase (SOD) and glutathione S-transferase (GST) important in scavenging free radicals. SOD is crucial in breaking down superoxide radicals, while GST conjugates harmful substances with

glutathione, facilitating their removal from cells (17). Studies have shown snail extracts can reduce inflammation, promote wound healing, and even exhibit anticancer activity (16, 18, 19). The secretions of *A. fulica* and *A. marginata* contain antioxidative glycosaminoglycans (20, 21). *Achatina* has been demonstrated to produce hyaluronic acid, allantoin and antimicrobial peptides and the antioxidant glycolic acid (21, 22). These bioactive products may explain the high antioxidant properties of *A. achatina* and *A. marginata* as shown in the results of the present study. Further research could focus on optimization of these properties for biopharmaceutical applications.

Conclusion

The results from this study revealed that the inhibition of nitric oxide radicals by the haemolymph of *A. achatina* and *A. marginata* was higher than that of the quercetin standard. Similarly, the inhibition of protein oxidation by *A. achatina* and *A. marginata* haemolymph was demonstrated,

although weaker than the Diclophenac standard as shown in the results of the present study. These bioactive products may explain the high antioxidant properties of *A. achatina* and *A. marginata* as shown in the results of the present study. Further research could focus on optimization of these properties for biopharmaceutical applications.

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Ethical Approval

All ethics were approved by the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Umugwo Research Ethics and Animal Care and Use – Sub Committee. Number: (UAES/URC/EAC/0010).

Conflicting Interest

The authors have declared no conflicting interests.

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